

Malnutrition in the Children Associated With Dietary Socio-Economic Risk Factors in the family

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ABSTRACT

Background: The growth or micronutrient status of an individual is termed as Nutritional Status. Malnutrition means there is a deficiency or excess of some nutrients in the body.

Aim: To find the risk factors and their association with Malnutrition.

Methodology: In this Cross-Sectional Study, we recorded data from 145 subjects coming for treatment of an illness in the OPD of Shalamar Hospital, based on Weight, Height, Head Circumference and Mid Upper Arm Circumference (MUAC). Risk factor includes Parents education, income, job status, dietary risk factors including consumption of fruits, vegetables and legumes etc.

Results: Out of 145 subjects, only 10(7%) had visited hospital. 103(71.7%) were male children, same in all age groups. MUAC identified that 16(11.3%) cases are Malnourished without severe Malnutrition. Median and Range of income was less in malnourished children as compared to children of normal MUAC. Malnourishment is also associated with low income and educational status of their fathers (p=0.04). Breastfeeding and nutritional intake of legumes, fruits, meat and eggs during weaning was identified to be less in malnourished cases. Differences between the 2-groups were statistically significant (p < 0.05).

Conclusion: The 12-Cases that are identified as Malnourished were associated with the Low-Income Status of their fathers; also these cases were also linked with the poor intake of nutrients.

Keywords: Risk factors, malnutrition, socioeconomic status

INTRODUCTION

Nutritional Status means the Growth of an Individual. Growth starts from the conception period till the infancy and then Infant becomes an Adult. Anthropometric measurements are the measurements that are used to check the Physical Dimensions of the human body (i.e. Size, Height, Weight, MUAC etc). In this study we used these anthropometric parameters to estimate the malnourishment status of the children aged 6-months to 5-years, as well as the cause of their malnourishment by the Everyday life Risk Factors.

METHODOLOGY

This cross-sectional study was conducted in the paediatrics OPD and ward of Services Hospital, Lahore from 1st July 2018 to 31st October 2018. Sample size was selected by Convenience Method to be 145. Sampling technique used was consecutive sampling.

RESULTS

We interviewed mothers of 164 children. Out of which, MUAC could not be measured in 3-Subjects. 16-Subjects were outside our specified age limit (i.e. 6-months to 5-years). Hence, the remaining children were 145, and they came hospital with some clinical signs and symptoms. Among these signs and symptoms, majority (53%) were due to some Communicable Diseases (n=77), and other (22%) are due to Non-communicable Diseases (n=32). Patients (children) with only fever as a sole symptom were (18%) and numbers are (n=26), and all other patients whose symptoms are due to Malnutrition like weakness,

fatigue and loss of appetite etc are (7%) and number (n=10). (Fig.1). 103 (71.7%) children are males and 40 were female children (i.e. 28.3%). Malnourishment was identified in only 16-Cases (i.e. 11%) out of 145, through Mean Upper Arm Circumference (MUAC). 12 were Male Children out 16 malnourished children.

Socio-Economic related risk factor: Regarding occupation of fathers; it shows that 27(18.9%) are low-skilled workers. Others includes businessmen, Govt. Employees & highly skilled workers were 41(28.3%) and then those of other variety of occupations were 77(52.8%).

Fig.1: Frequency of complaints with which child presented at hospital. (n=85)

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Table 6: Comparison of Mid upper arm measurements with age & gender of the subjects.

Age in Years	MUAC (1-5 Years) Malnourished			Total
	Normal	Male	Female	
1-2	27	10	3	40
2-3	36	2	0	38
3-5	33+34	0	0	67

Fig 2: Bar Diagram showing frequency of the occupation of the father of the subjects (N=145)

DISCUSSIONS

Malnutrition means there is a deficiency or excess of some nutrients in the body. There are studies that find association of child's malnutrition with some family and socioeconomic risk factors. This study aims at finding these risk factors and their association with Malnutrition. Growth starts from the conception period till the infancy and then Infant becomes an adult. Anthropometric measurements are the measurements that are used to check the Physical Dimensions of the human body (i.e. size, height, weight, MUAC etc). In this study we used these anthropometric parameters to estimate the malnourishment status of the children aged 6-months to 5-years, as well as the cause of their malnourishment by the everyday life risk factors. among these signs and symptoms, majority (53%) were due to some Communicable Diseases (n=77), and other (22%) are due to non-communicable Diseases (n=32). Patients (children) with only fever as a sole symptom were (18%) and numbers are (n=26), and all other patients whose symptoms are due to Malnutrition like weakness, fatigue and loss of appetite etc are 10(7%).

CONCLUSION

The 12-Cases that are identified as Malnourished were associated with the Low-Income Status of their fathers; also these cases were also linked with the poor intake of nutrients such as fruits, fresh meats and Legumes etc.

REFERENCES

1. Victora CG, Adair L, Fall C, Hallal PC, Martorell R, Richter L, Sachdev HS, Maternal and Child Undernutrition Study Group. Maternal and child undernutrition: consequences for adult

health and human capital. *The lancet*. 2008 Jan 26;371(9609):340-57.

2. Abuja N. National Population Commission and ICF Macro; 2009. National Population Commission (NPC)[Nigeria] and ICF Macro Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey. 2008.
3. Basit A, Nair S, Chakraborty KB, Darshan BB, Kamath A. Risk factors for under-nutrition among children aged one to five years in Udupi taluk of Karnataka, India: A case control study. *The Australasian medical journal*. 2012;5(3):163.
4. Lima MD, Motta ME, Santos EC, Silva GA. Determinants of impaired growth among hospitalized children: a case-control study. *São Paulo Medical Journal*. 2004 May;122(3):117-23.
5. Alam DS, Marks GC, Baqui AH, Yunus M, Fuchs GJ. Association between clinical type of diarrhoea and growth of children under 5 years in rural Bangladesh. *International journal of epidemiology*. 2000 Oct 1;29(5):916-21.
6. Ikeda N, Irie Y, Shibuya K. Determinants of reduced child stunting in Cambodia: analysis of pooled data from three demographic and health surveys. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*. 2013;91:341-9.
7. Ali SS, Karim N, Billoo AG, Haider SS. Association of literacy of mothers with malnutrition among children under three years of age in rural area of district Malir, Karachi. *children*. 2005 Dec 1;9:10.
8. Vorster HH, Kruger A. Poverty, malnutrition, underdevelopment and cardiovascular disease: a South African perspective. *Cardiovascular journal of Africa*. 2007 Jul;18(5):321.
9. Mujib SA, Kazmi T, Khan S, Shad MA, Bashir M, Khan B. Relationship of non-organic factors with malnutrition among children under three years of age. *Journal of the College of Physicians and Surgeons--Pakistan: JCPSP*. 2006 May;16(5):355-8.
10. Rana MN, Kazi MY, Nasir A, Hussain A. Prevalence of risk factors of primary 3rd degree malnutrition in children under 5 years of age; admitted in Services Hospital, Lahore. *Annals of King Edward Medical University*. 2006;12(2): 208-9.